

MORAL-AESTHETIC EDUCATION OF STUDENTS ENGAGED IN WRESTLING.

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Abstract. *In the consistent implementation of reforms in our country, special attention is paid to the issue of forming the physical and spiritual health of the growing young generation, striving for a healthy lifestyle, and increasing the love of young people for sports. Young people are the most active category of society, if young people are interested in physical culture and sports activities and it causes positive changes, we can talk about the impact of physical exercises on personal development.*

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In the consistent implementation of reforms in our country, special attention is paid to the issue of forming the physical and spiritual health of the growing young generation, striving for a healthy lifestyle, and increasing the love of young people for sports. Young people are the most active category of society, if young people are interested in physical culture and sports activities and it causes positive changes, we can talk about the impact of physical exercises on personal development. In the 2017-2021 Action Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "in the process of educating physically healthy, spiritually and mentally developed, independent-thinking, loyal to the Motherland, with a firm outlook on life, deepening democratic reforms and civil society development increase their social activity" [1] such priority tasks are defined and serve to form students today on the basis of moral and aesthetic education.

Improving the process of moral-aesthetic education in the system of spot schools for teenagers is one of the most important and urgent tasks. It is important to make students who are engaged in wrestling feel moral-aesthetic concepts, faith, honesty, religion, honor, modesty, and beauty. receiving and similar human qualities do not develop by themselves. Underlying all this is education. Among them, the significance of Bolalar adolescent spot schools is great in educating people with perfection, thirst for knowledge, willpower, mental and moral qualities, aesthetic taste [2].

Special attention is paid to the principles, factors, system, condition and essence of future wrestlers' moral and aesthetic upbringing in order to improve the personality of the students engaged in wrestling in children's and teenagers' spot schools. The principles of moral-aesthetic education are as follows:

- the age of students engaged in wrestling, their individual psychological characteristics, the initial level of moral and aesthetic education;
- students engaged in wrestling will be taught systematicity, consistency, gradualism, integrity, interdependence between disciplines, sequence, integrativeness;
- technicality, unity and integrity of students engaged in wrestling;
- to use all didactic principles of students engaged in wrestling;
- regularity of students engaged in wrestling, from raising a problem to solving it;

- the advantage of positivity, exemplariness, demonstrativeness, striving for the ideal among students engaged in wrestling;

- to harmonize the educational process of students engaged in wrestling, the moral and aesthetic education of future specialists, and the development of their personality with humanitarian ideas;

- cultural compatibility of students engaged in wrestling is connected with national-cultural, universal, moral-aesthetic values;

- personalization of struggling students - attention to the individual, attention to his preferences, his choices, his self-expression in studies and life, and so on.

It is known that moral-aesthetic education is inextricably linked with moral-aesthetic outlook. Because worldview is also formed in the process of education [5].

Just as a well-rounded, well-rounded personality of students engaged in wrestling is formed in the process of education, the moral and aesthetic worldview of a person develops in this process. After all, education is a form of pedagogical process aimed at a specific goal, consciously implemented, aimed at mastering social experiences: knowledge, skills and abilities, creative activity methods, social and spiritual relations. Through education, social experiences are mastered, knowledge is transformed into trust and faith, behavior and outlook are formed, the essence of beauty in material and spiritual life is studied, and moral-aesthetic relationships between people are perceived. , creative activity is formed. Therefore, it is not appropriate to treat education as a simple event. "Education is a process that continues forever in society, and is a complete pedagogical system with its structural structure: goal, material base, principle, law and methods, forms and means, subject-object, management and achieving results. As in other social structures, education makes it necessary to observe certain laws in its organization. Accordingly, the laws of education are considered to be strong, repeated and basic relationships in the educational process, and are an effective result of the formation and development of a person [2].

Ethical and aesthetic education of the students of children's and teenagers' sport schools engaged in wrestling through sports holidays is organized based on the demands and needs of the society. In the moral-aesthetic education of wrestling students, it serves to develop moral-aesthetic faith, moral-aesthetic ideal, moral-aesthetic thinking, loyalty to moral-aesthetic values. This process also follows certain rules for students engaged in wrestling. Legitimacy is the appearance of the relationship of things and events in reality, a component that means the necessity of something to appear, and as a philosophical concept, a set of rules and instructions that determine the behavior, behavior, and manners of a person in society. These laws are considered to be a characteristic feature of the pedagogical process, the structural aggregate of this process, i.e., the goal, content, method, organization, management, conditions, opportunities that ensure the development of education and personal moral-aesthetic education. represents integrity and connectedness. In the pedagogical process, all components of education are interconnected [3].

It will be effective for both the society and the specialist if the activities of the students engaged in wrestling, who are preparing for the future specialty, are useful for the country, appropriate for the purpose, and their relations are rationally organized. At this point, it should be recognized that the relationship between people is formed in the process of activity and achieves its goal. The advanced pedagogical and psychological teaching of students engaged in wrestling shows that a person is formed and develops as a person in the process of his relationship to reality, social environment and other people. The formation and development of students engaged in wrestling

as individuals is the finding of relationships in the process of human activity. For example, subjects of educational institutions - tutors, professors, school administration, students, parents, school teams and their organizations, neighborhood, etc. interpersonal relations in communities create an educational relationship and they are important for the formation and development of valuable personal qualities and qualities for a person. Therefore, the recognition of activity and attitude in the process of educational and educational work in children's and teenagers' spot schools is considered the basis and source of the development of the student's moral and aesthetic worldview. Based on the requirement of the principle of the development of the process of moral-aesthetic education, it can be said that the process of moral-aesthetic education of students will not only consist of physical education classes organized on the basis of a theoretical schedule. Therefore, as a continuation of this process, in addition to the auditorium, spiritual and educational events are also of great importance. Because in the course of spiritual and educational activities held outside the auditorium, physical education events serve to fully satisfy the demand for movement. In particular, various sports clubs ("Young gymnast", "Wrestling", "Football", "Volleyball", etc.), sports competitions, sports holidays, meetings, excursions, training, etc. are included in the sports events organized outside the auditorium. . Among them, various sports holidays are of particular importance in the moral and aesthetic education of students in children's and teenagers' spot schools. Because the importance of sports holidays and its role in the physical education of students in the Children's Spot Schools is important for the country and for every family, and above all, in raising a healthy child. At the same time, the growing young generation also acquires perfection in terms of moral and aesthetics.

Ethical and aesthetic education of students engaged in wrestling has its own rules and principles as a component of the process of universal education. These rules and principles are derived from the rules and principles of universal education. Laws and principles of moral and aesthetic education of students engaged in wrestling serve to educate a well-rounded person in all aspects.

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